

Reappraisal of QED fundamentals

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Abstract: The Quantum Electrodynamics fundamental drawbacks are revisited and analyzed. Those concern the vector potential amplitude operator, the electromagnetic field harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian with the associated zero-point energy singularity and the electron-vacuum interaction Hamiltonian. Without stating postulates or advancing any hypothesis it is shown that the QED difficulties can be readily overcome by enhancing the quantization of the vector potential amplitude to a single photon level. A photon wave function is defined as a probability density normalized within an intrinsic quantization volume and satisfying Schrödinger's equation for both the photon energy and vector potential. Ensuing the single photon vector potential quantization the electromagnetic vacuum appears naturally complementing the normal ordering Hamiltonian without involving singularities.

1. Introduction

QED is without any doubt among the most successful theories developed in modern physics for the description of light-matter interactions at the atomic and molecular scale. However, despite the numerous achievements and the impressive precision of some theoretical predictions compared to the experiments, the QED theory still involves some fundamental aspects leading to ambiguities and singularities [1-3]. For many decades, the last ones had not really a direct impact to the majority of the applications until recent astrophysical observations on the cosmic expansion have shown that the quantum vacuum energy density is finite and extremely low contradicting the singularity of the zero-point energy in QED and in quantum field theory in general [4-10]. Hence, the well validated astrophysical investigations generated an increasing interest last years towards the comprehension of the real nature of the quantum vacuum looking for new representations overcoming the well-known singularity of the zero-point energy issued from the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian.

On the other hand, in order to define the vector potential amplitude operators of a single photon in QED the classical and quantum energy density equivalence has been considered involving an external volume which is not an intrinsic photon physical property [1-3, 11]. Although the vector potential natural units are proportional to a frequency, the defined single photon vector potential amplitude in QED is proportional to the inverse square root of the frequency yielding unphysical consequences. Thus, the dependence on frequency of the photon vector potential and that of the corresponding electromagnetic fields are conflictual entailing a fundamental physical incoherence. Finally, the well-known difficulties encountered for establishing a photon wave function are mainly due to the photon point particle concept yielding major constraints for establishing a position operator [12-17].

In what follows we first discuss extensively the origin of the above QED fundamental drawbacks and next we show how the enhancement of the vector potential amplitude to a single photon level permits to remedy to all these theoretical inconveniences.

2. Fundamental ambiguities in QED theory

2.1. Photon vector potential amplitude operators

In order to define the vector potential amplitude operators for a single k -mode photon with angular frequency ω_k , the mean value over a period of the energy density $\langle W \rangle_T$ of a monochromatic plane wave is put equal to the energy density of a single photon considered in a cavity with volume V [1,2,11]

$$\langle W \rangle_T = 2\varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 |a_{0k}(\omega_k)|^2 \equiv \frac{\hbar \omega_k}{V} \rightarrow a_{0k}(\omega_k) = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0 \omega_k V}} \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k)$ is the k -mode electromagnetic plane wave vector potential amplitude, $\hbar$ is Planck's reduced constant and ε_0 is the vacuum electric permittivity.

Based on the classical-quantum energy density equivalence imposed above, the vector potential amplitude operators for a single photon are defined in QED [1,2,18] by associating the k -mode and λ -polarization photon annihilation and creation non-Hermitian operators, $a_{k\lambda}$ and $a_{k\lambda}^+$ respectively, to the established expression of the vector potential amplitude (1)

$$\tilde{a}_{k\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_k V}} a_{k\lambda} \quad ; \quad \tilde{a}_{k\lambda}^* = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_k V}} a_{k\lambda}^+ \quad (2)$$

Therein, we note that the left hand side of (1) is totally independent on any external parameter while this is not the case for the right hand side which depends on the external volume V . Consequently, the above expressions yield an unphysical result for a free of cavity photon, that is for $V \rightarrow \infty$. In fact, in this physical situation the vector potential amplitude should vanish entailing a zero photon energy. Obviously, this conflicts with the experimental evidence and particularly for the photons detected from outer space. Certainly, we could consider that for a photon in an infinite cavity the energy density in the right hand side of (1) tends to zero, which is a quite physical result. But in this case the equation (1) does not hold since the left hand side remains unaffected.

Under these conditions, we may naturally wonder how the application of equation (2) in QED could give correct and physical results. The answer lays in the general expression of the vector potential which is considered as a superposition of the vector potentials of all the single k -mode photons

$$\tilde{A}(\vec{r}, t) = \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_k V}} \sum_{\lambda=1}^2 \left[\alpha_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} + \alpha_{k\lambda}^+ e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \right] \quad (3)$$

where the summations run over all the modes k and both polarizations λ , circular left and right, with $\hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}$ the polarization complex unit vector. Also, $\vec{k}$ is the wave-vector with amplitude $|\vec{k}| = 2\pi / \lambda_k$ where λ_k is the wavelength of the mode k and θ a phase parameter.

In calculations involving the square of the vector potential, e.g. for the energy density, the external parameter V is eliminated by using the following transformation deduced from the density of states theory [1,2,18]

$$\sum_k \rightarrow \frac{V}{2\pi^2 c^3} \int \omega^2 d\omega \quad (4)$$

By this way we can get precise results compared to the experiments and independent on the volume parameter V . However, it is important noting here that the transformation (4) is valid for any shape of the volume V under the condition that all the photons wavelengths are much smaller than the characteristic dimensions of V , that is

$$\lambda_k \ll V^{1/3} \quad (\forall k) \quad (5)$$

Consequently, for a large number of photons following the condition (5) the vector potential formalism described above is quite efficient in QED but the ambiguity related to a single photon issued from (1) still remains.

Therein, the relation (1) yields another fundamental question. In fact, the general solution of the vector potential issued from Maxwell's equation writes with the well-known expression [19,20]

$$\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} \int \frac{\vec{J}(\vec{r}', t - |\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|/c)}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d^3r' \quad (6)$$

where $\vec{J}$ is the current density, c is the speed of light in vacuum and μ is the magnetic permeability.

A careful unit analysis of (6) shows that the vector potential is physically proportional to a frequency. This is in contradiction with the vector potential amplitude obtained in (1) which is inversely proportional to the square root of the frequency.

In addition, using (1) the electric field amplitude of a single photon writes [1,2,18]

$$|\vec{\mathcal{E}}_k| = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{2\varepsilon_0 V}} \quad (7)$$

Comparison between equations (1) and (7) leads to the unphysical conclusion that the higher the frequency the lower the photon vector potential amplitude and the higher the photon electric field. We will see later that the solution to these ambiguities lies in the volume parameter V .

2.2 Origin of the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian of the electromagnetic field

The total energy of a multimode electromagnetic field considered in a volume V writes in classical theory with the equally well-known expression [1,2]

$$E_{EM} = \sum_{k,\lambda} 2\varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 V |\vec{a}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)|^2 \quad (8)$$

where $\vec{a}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ is the vector potential of a single k -mode and λ -polarization plane wave.

Replacing in (8) the single k -mode photon vector potential amplitude operators defined in (2) we get the following two expressions for the quantum mechanics Hamiltonian of the electromagnetic field

$$\tilde{H}_{NO} = \sum_{k,\lambda} a_{k\lambda}^+ a_{k\lambda} \hbar \omega_k \rightarrow E_{NO} = \sum_{k,\lambda} n_{k\lambda} \hbar \omega_k \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{H}_{ANO} = \sum_{k,\lambda} a_{k\lambda} a_{k\lambda}^+ \hbar \omega_k \rightarrow E_{ANO} = \sum_{k,\lambda} (n_{k\lambda} + 1) \hbar \omega_k \quad (10)$$

where $\tilde{H}_{NO}$ corresponds to the normal ordering Hamiltonian and $\tilde{H}_{ANO}$ to the antinormal ordering one, E_{NO} and E_{ANO} are the corresponding eigenvalues while $n_{k\lambda}$ is the total number of k -mode and λ -polarization photons. Also, for $\tilde{H}_{ANO}$ we have used the fundamental commutation relation $[a_{k\lambda}, a_{k'\lambda'}^+] = \delta_{kk'} \delta_{\lambda\lambda'}$.

The mean value of the last two Hamiltonians yields a harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian which is usually introduced in QED as the natural Hamiltonian of the electromagnetic field [1,2,21]

$$\tilde{H}_{EM} = \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{H}_{NO} + \tilde{H}_{ANO}) = \sum_{k,\lambda} \left(a_{k\lambda}^+ a_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \hbar \omega_k \rightarrow E = \sum_{k,\lambda} \left(n_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \hbar \omega_k \quad (11)$$

Following this operation the electromagnetic field is considered to be composed of single mode harmonic oscillators corresponding to single photon states.

It is of crucial importance to remark here that we have absolutely no physical reason based on the experimental evidence to consider the mean values of the normal and antinormal ordering Hamiltonians in order to obtain a harmonic oscillator one. As we will see later this arbitrary mathematical operation leads to unphysical results compared to the observations.

Now, a different way is also often used in order to establish a harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian for the electromagnetic field. It is based on the canonical variables of position $Q_{k\lambda}$ and momentum $P_{k\lambda}$. The vector potential amplitude and its complex conjugate can be expressed through the position and momentum variables as follows [1,2,18]

$$a_{k\lambda} = \frac{(\omega_k Q_{k\lambda} + iP_{k\lambda})}{2\omega_k \sqrt{\varepsilon_0 V}} \quad ; \quad a_{k\lambda}^* = \frac{(\omega_k Q_{k\lambda} - iP_{k\lambda})}{2\omega_k \sqrt{\varepsilon_0 V}} \quad (12)$$

Using the above expressions in equation (8) the classical electromagnetic field energy writes

$$E_{EM} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k,\lambda} (P_{k\lambda}^2 + \omega_k^2 Q_{k\lambda}^2) \pm i\omega_k [Q_{k\lambda}, P_{k\lambda}] \quad (13)$$

where the (+) sign is obtained with the normal ordering, $a_{k\lambda}^* a_{k\lambda}$, and the (-) one with the antinormal ordering, $a_{k\lambda} a_{k\lambda}^*$.

At that level, since $Q_{k\lambda}$ and $P_{k\lambda}$ are simply canonical variables and not quantum mechanics operators it is generally considered in the literature that the commutation term in (13) vanishes imposing $[Q_{k\lambda}, P_{k\lambda}] = 0$. In this way, a harmonic oscillator expression is obtained for the classical electromagnetic field energy

$$E_{EM} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k,\lambda} (P_{k\lambda}^2 + \omega_k^2 Q_{k\lambda}^2) \quad (14)$$

Replacing in the last equation the canonical variables of position and momentum with the corresponding quantum mechanics Hermitian operators [1,2,18]

$$\tilde{P}_{k\lambda} = i\sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega_k}{2}}(a_{k\lambda}^+ - a_{k\lambda}) \quad ; \quad \tilde{Q}_{k\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_k}}(a_{k\lambda}^+ + a_{k\lambda}) \quad (15)$$

we get the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian for the electromagnetic field

$$\tilde{H}_{EM} = \sum_{k,\lambda} \left(a_{k\lambda}^+ a_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \hbar\omega_k \rightarrow E = \sum_{k,\lambda} \left(n_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \hbar\omega_k \quad (16)$$

It is of high importance to underline here that, for a particle harmonic oscillator with mass $m \neq 0$ and momentum $\vec{p} = m d\vec{q} / dt$, with the canonical variables of position $Q = |\vec{q}| \sqrt{m}$ and momentum $P = |\vec{p}| / \sqrt{m}$ the transition from the classical expression of energy

$$E = \frac{1}{2} (P^2 + \omega^2 Q^2) \quad (17)$$

to the quantum mechanics Hamiltonian,

$$\tilde{H} = \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{P}^2 + \omega^2 \tilde{Q}^2) = \hbar\omega \left(a^+ a + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (18)$$

where $\tilde{Q} = \sqrt{\hbar/2\omega}(a^+ + a)$ and $\tilde{P} = i\sqrt{\hbar\omega/2}(a^+ - a)$, is direct and needs no commutation operations between the canonical variables P and Q [2,22].

Consequently, for a massive particle the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian obtained in (18) is a direct result expressing a real physical state, e.g. phonons in solid state physics [23].

Conversely, in the case of the electromagnetic field a commutation operation appears between the canonical variables $Q_{k\lambda}$ and $P_{k\lambda}$ during the transition from (8) to (13). Consequently, cancelling the commutation term $[Q_{k\lambda}, P_{k\lambda}]$ in (13) in order to obtain (14) just before replacing the canonical variables by the corresponding quantum mechanics operators is not mathematically correct. It is extremely important to underline here that Heisenberg's commutation relation $[\tilde{Q}_{k\lambda}, \tilde{P}_{k'\lambda'}] = i\hbar\delta_{kk'}\delta_{\lambda\lambda'}$ is a fundamental concept of quantum mechanics which has to be taken into account when replacing classical canonical variables by the corresponding quantum mechanics operators. Hence, keeping the commutation term $[Q_{k\lambda}, P_{k\lambda}]$ in (13) and then substituting the classical variables by the corresponding quantum operators (15) we obtain the same normal ordering and anti-normal ordering Hamiltonians as in (9) and (10)

$$\tilde{H}_{EM}^{(+)} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k,\lambda} (\tilde{P}_{k\lambda}^2 + \omega_k^2 \tilde{Q}_{k\lambda}^2) + i\omega_k [\tilde{Q}_{k\lambda}, \hat{P}_{k'\lambda'}] \rightarrow \tilde{H}_{NO} = \sum_{k,\lambda} a_{k\lambda}^+ a_{k\lambda} \hbar\omega_k \rightarrow E_{NO} = \sum_{k,\lambda} n_{k\lambda} \hbar\omega_k \quad (19)$$

$$\tilde{H}_{EM}^{(-)} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k,\lambda} (\tilde{P}_{k\lambda}^2 + \omega_k^2 \tilde{Q}_{k\lambda}^2) - i\omega_k [\tilde{Q}_{k\lambda}, \tilde{P}_{k'\lambda'}] \rightarrow \tilde{H}_{ANO} = \sum_{k,\lambda} a_{k\lambda} a_{k\lambda}^+ \hbar\omega_k \rightarrow E_{ANO} = \sum_{k,\lambda} (n_{k\lambda} + 1) \hbar\omega_k \quad (20)$$

Obviously, the mathematical ambiguity consisting of suppressing the classical variables commutation term $[Q_{k\lambda}, P_{k\lambda}]$ just before replacing the classical variables by the non-commuting quantum mechanics operators $[\tilde{Q}_{k\lambda}, \tilde{P}_{k'\lambda'}] = i\hbar\delta_{kk'}\delta_{\lambda\lambda'}$ leads to the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian [2,24,25].

It is clear that it is impossible to get a harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian for the electromagnetic field without taking arbitrarily the mean value of the normal and antinormal ordering Hamiltonians or without neglecting Heisenberg's uncertainty in the position-momentum treatment [2,21]. It comes out that considering the mean value of the normal and antinormal ordering Hamiltonians implies inadvertently the drop of Heisenberg's uncertainty relation.

Finally, it is also worth noting that for all the other fields the operations leading to the zero-point energy are equivalent and consequently the same remarks may also apply.

2.3 The zero-point energy singularity and the physical consequences

In total absence of photons, that is for $n_{k\lambda} = 0$ in (11) or (16) we get the well-known zero-point energy of the electromagnetic field corresponding to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum

$$E_{ZPE} = \sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k \quad (21)$$

whose energy density in any volume V in space is

$$\rho_{ZPE} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k \rightarrow \infty \quad (22)$$

This is the principal singularity in QED theory, the energy density of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum is infinite at any point in space [26].

Equation (22) is a pure mathematical result, issued from the eigenstates of the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian and should normally represent a real physical state yielding tremendous cosmological consequences [10]. Despite of this, it is often claimed in the literature that the zero-point energy is an “unobserved quantity”. It is systematically quoted behind an elegant phraseology consisting of “virtual vacuum photons” or “vacuum fluctuations” although equation (22) does not represent any fluctuations or any virtual vacuum states [7,9,10].

Now, recent well-validated astrophysical observations upon the cosmic acceleration estimated the vacuum energy density to be finite and extremely low, roughly $\rho_{ZPE}^{obs} \sim 10^{-10} J m^{-3}$ contradicting the theoretical statement resulting from the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian [4-10]. Following the observational evidence we are now constrained to find a finite value for the zero-point energy density. Our knowledge of the QCD vacuum state is extremely elusive but QED offers a readily comprehensive framework for estimating the zero-point energy density. Thus, we can get a finite value by upper limiting the modes number. Transforming the discrete summation in (22) into a continuous one, according to the density of state theory (4), we obtain an integration over the frequencies which is also infinite [26]

$$\rho_{ZPE} = \frac{\hbar}{2\pi^2 c^3} \int_0^{\infty} \omega^3 d\omega \rightarrow \infty \quad (23)$$

It is generally considered that the higher possible photon frequency beyond which the energy density transforms the photon into a black hole should be roughly $\sim 10^{43}$ Hz corresponding to Planck’s energy 10^{19} GeV. Thus, replacing the upper limit of the integration in (23) by Planck’s frequency we get a theoretical value for the electromagnetic quantum vacuum energy density $\rho_{ZPE}^{th} \sim 10^{110} J m^{-3}$.

Considering the zero-point energy contribution of all the other known fields does not changes radically this result which is in disagreement with the experimental observations by a factor of 120 orders of magnitude [7,9,10]. This is the worst theoretical prediction in the history of science and has been called by many authors “vacuum catastrophe”. Consequently, the experimental evidence implies that the zero-point energy issued from the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian does not correspond to a real physical state.

In reality, there is no experimental evidence that a single photon state is a harmonic oscillator entailing that there is no physical reason for considering the mean value of the normal and antinormal ordering Hamiltonians in order to obtain a harmonic oscillator one [2,21]. This is also the reason why in QED the normal ordering Hamiltonian is principally used casting aside the zero point energy singularity.

On the other hand, it is also widespread that the zero-point energy represented by equation (21) is at the origin of the quantum vacuum effects such as the spontaneous emission, the Lamb shift or even the Casimir effect.

Therein, we recall that the spontaneous emission and the Lamb shift are calculated in QED based on the properties of the single photon creation $a_{k\lambda}^+$ and annihilation $a_{k\lambda}$ operators without invoking at all the zero point energy term $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ which is a constant and commutes with all quantum mechanics operators.

Indeed, the interaction Hamiltonian between an electron and the quantum vacuum vanishes

$$H_{\text{int}} = -e\vec{r} \cdot \frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\tilde{A}(\vec{r}, t), \sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k \right] = 0 \quad (24)$$

entailing that the zero-point energy term has absolutely no physical impact to the spontaneous emission and the Lamb shift.

Regarding the well-known Casimir effect it has been demonstrated by many studies using different approaches [27-30] that it is physically due to Lorentz's forces or source fields and not to the zero-point energy.

Thus, as quoted by many authors, it is clear that skipping the zero-point energy by considering only the normal ordering Hamiltonian do not compromise any of the achievements related to the calculation of the vacuum effects in QED [2,29,30].

To conclude, the zero point energy term $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ ensuing from the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian of

the electromagnetic field is obtained by considering without any valuable physical reason the mean value of the normal and antinormal ordering Hamiltonians and neglecting Heisenberg's uncertainty. In addition, this term is not involved in the vacuum effects in QED and conflicts strongly with the astrophysical observational evidence. Consequently, the vacuum concept in QED had to be reappraised and we may reasonably wonder which physical vacuum representation could be more appropriate to complement the normal ordering Hamiltonian.

3. Remedying QED fundamental drawbacks

In what follows, without stating postulates or axioms, we enhance the quantization of the vector potential to a single photon level and we show that all the above ambiguities and singularities in the QED formalism are naturally overcome.

3.1. Photon quantization volume, an intrinsic geometrical property.

It is obvious that for the equation (1) to hold physically the parameter V should correspond to the characteristic quantization volume of a single photon state. Such a space dependence of the photon may be deduced directly from the density of states theory [1,2]. In fact, the number of photons $dn(\omega)$ in a given quantization volume V in the frequency interval between ω and $\omega+d\omega$ writes

$$dn(\omega) = 4V \frac{\omega^2}{\pi^2 c^3} d\omega \quad (25)$$

where we have considered the two photon spin states, corresponding classically to circular left and right helicity, and the two possible directions along the same propagation axis.

Integrating (25) implies that a quantization volume can be assigned to a single k -mode photon

$$V_k = \left(\frac{3}{4} \pi^2 c^3 \right) \omega_k^{-3} \approx 0.029 \lambda_k^3 \quad (26)$$

This is compatible with the theoretical concept that a photon extends over a wavelength [2,3,31] and also with the experimental observations which have shown its lateral extension is proportional to a fraction of the wavelength [32-35] entailing that, since Mandel's experiments [36,37], a photon can only be localized within a volume proportional to the cube of the wavelength [1-3,18].

Hence, introducing (26) in (1) we get the vector potential amplitude for a single k -mode photon

$$\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = \pm \frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{2\hbar}{3\varepsilon_0 c^3}} \omega_k = \xi \omega_k \quad (27)$$

It is important underlying here that the obtained photon vector potential amplitude is now proportional to the frequency and thus compatible with the natural units of the vector potential. The proportionality of the photon vector potential amplitude to the frequency has already been deduced previously applying a different methodology [38,39]. Also, ξ has both positive and negative values confirming that the photon is its own antiparticle as always suspected in the particle theory.

Although the result of the integration of (25) does not yield a pure integer, the vector potential amplitude constant $\xi = \pm \sqrt{2\hbar/3\varepsilon_0 c^3} / \pi$ obtained in (27) by the density of states theory is an excellent

approximation. A more precise value of ξ can be obtained by normalizing the mean energy of single mode plane electromagnetic wave over a period to the single photon energy [40,41]

$$E_k = \left\langle \int \varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \xi^2 \omega_k^2 \left[\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} + \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)}^* e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} \right]^2 d^3 r \right\rangle_T = \hbar \omega_k \quad (28)$$

where L,R corresponds to left or right circular polarization respectively.

We draw the expression of the constant ξ

$$\xi = \pm \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{8\alpha \varepsilon_0 c^3}} = \frac{\hbar}{4\pi e c} \quad (29)$$

where $\alpha = e^2 / (4\pi\varepsilon_0)\hbar c \approx 1/137$ is the fine structure constant and e the electron-positron charge.

Introducing $\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = \xi\omega_k = (\hbar/4\pi e c)\omega_k$ in (1) we get the photon quantization volume depending on the vector potential amplitude ξ

$$V_k = \left(\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2} \right) \omega_k^{-3} = 4\alpha \lambda_k^3 \approx 0.029 \lambda_k^3 \quad (30)$$

which numerically is roughly equivalent to (26) obtained from the density of states theory showing the self-consistency of the calculation.

Therein, it is important noting that the electron-positron charge, a fundamental physical constant, issues naturally during the energy normalization procedure (28) and is directly related to the photon vector potential amplitude quantization constant ξ [40,42,43]

$$e = (4\pi)^2 \alpha \xi / \mu_0 \quad (31)$$

where μ_0 is the vacuum magnetic permeability.

The last expression relates the photon vector potential amplitude constant to the positive-negative elementary charge which puts the basis for understanding the mechanism of the photons to electron-positrons mutual transformations. It is worthy investigating whether the electrons and positrons, more generally leptons and antileptons, are standing states of photons in specific spatial configurations (toroidal or other) as already suggested previously [44].

3.2. Single photon electric and magnetic fields.

We can now express the vector potential of an electromagnetic k -mode in classical and quantum representations using the defined vector potential amplitude in (27)

$$\vec{\alpha}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \omega_k \left[\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} + \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)}^* e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} \right] = \omega_k \vec{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (32)$$

$$\vec{\alpha}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \omega_k \left[\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)} a_{k(L,R)} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} + \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)}^* a_{k(L,R)}^+ e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} \right] = \omega_k \vec{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (33)$$

The precession of the quantized vector potential around the propagation axis at the angular frequency ω_k , generates orthogonal electric $\vec{\varepsilon}_k$ and magnetic $\vec{\beta}_k$ fields [25,40,45,46] whose strengths, that is the square root of the sum of the squares of the components, are obtained straightforward

$$\vec{\varepsilon}_k = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \xi \omega_k \left(\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} + \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)}^* e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} \right) \rightarrow \|\vec{\varepsilon}_k\| = \sqrt{2} |\xi| \omega_k^2 \quad (34)$$

$$\vec{\beta}_k = \vec{\nabla} \times \xi \omega_k \left(\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} + \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{k(L,R)}^* e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t+\theta)} \right) \rightarrow \|\vec{\beta}_k\| = \sqrt{2\varepsilon_0 \mu_0} |\xi| \omega_k^2 \quad (35)$$

Note that they are proportional to the square of the frequency and independent on any external volume parameter.

The fact that the photon electric field amplitude is proportional to the square of the frequency may lead to a vacuum energy density compatible with the recent astrophysical observations related to the cosmic acceleration [47].

Also, the established photon electric and magnetic fields satisfy Maxwell's equations

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{\varepsilon}_k = -\frac{\partial \vec{\beta}_k}{\partial t} \quad \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\varepsilon}_k = 0 \quad (36)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{\beta}_k = \varepsilon_0 \mu_0 \frac{\partial \vec{\varepsilon}_k}{\partial t} \quad \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\beta}_k = 0 \quad (37)$$

considered in vacuum and in absence of charges.

3.3. The photon quantization volume and Heisenberg's uncertainty

The single photon vector potential amplitude operators now write

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda} = \xi \omega_k \alpha_{k\lambda} \quad ; \quad \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}^* = \xi \omega_k \alpha_{k\lambda}^+ \quad (38)$$

On the other hand, the position and momentum Hermitian operators are expressed respectively as follows [1,2,18]

$$\tilde{Q}_{k\lambda} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_0 V_k} (\tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda} + \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}^*) \quad ; \quad \tilde{P}_{k\lambda} = -i \omega_k \sqrt{\varepsilon_0 V_k} (\tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda} - \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}^*) \quad (39)$$

Using now (30) in the last expressions of position and momentum operators it is straightforward to demonstrate Heisenberg's commutation relation

$$\left[\tilde{Q}_{k\lambda}, \tilde{P}_{k'\lambda'} \right] = -i \varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \omega_{k'} \sqrt{V_k V_{k'}} \left[(\xi a_{k\lambda} + \xi a_{k\lambda}^+), (\xi a_{k'\lambda'} - \xi a_{k'\lambda'}^+) \right] = i \hbar \delta_{kk'} \delta_{\lambda\lambda'} \quad (40)$$

showing that the position-momentum uncertainty for the photon, an intrinsic physical property, lays on the characteristic quantization volume.

Indeed, it is now easy to express the particle properties of the photon, energy and momentum, through the classical electromagnetic functions integrated over the quantization volume V_k and considering circular polarization

$$E_k = \int_{V_k} 2 \varepsilon_0 \alpha_{0k}^2 (\omega_k) \omega_k^2 d^3 r = \int_{V_k} 2 \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 d^3 r = 2 \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k = \hbar \omega_k \quad (41)$$

$$\vec{p}_k = \int_{V_k} \varepsilon_0 \vec{\varepsilon}_k \times \vec{\beta}_k d^3 r = \varepsilon_0 \left(\sqrt{2} \xi \omega_k^2 \right) \left(\sqrt{2 \varepsilon_0 \mu_0} \xi \omega_k^2 \right) V_k \vec{k} / |\vec{k}| = \hbar \vec{k} \quad (42)$$

where for the momentum we have used the photon electric and magnetic fields established above in (34) and (35).

Obviously, the photon energy and momentum are not carried by a point particle but by a wave-corpucle within a precise quantization volume [25,40].

Consequently, the photon is not a point particle and constitutes a particular case in the standard particle model. According to (30), the spatial dimensions of the photon may vary from femtometers, for high-energy γ rays, to cosmic dimensions for extremely low frequency radio waves. The photon quantization volume also entails a physical explanation why a photon position operator cannot be defined and can only be expressed through the quantization volume as in (39).

3.4. The photon wave function

It can be easily shown that the vector potential function $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ with the quantized amplitude expressed in (32) satisfies Maxwell's propagation equation in vacuum,

$$\vec{\nabla}_k^2 \vec{\alpha}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \vec{\alpha}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = 0 \quad (43)$$

as well as Schrödinger's equation with the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian

$$i \hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \tilde{H}_k \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (44)$$

where $\tilde{H}_k = \hbar \tilde{\omega}_k = -i \hbar c \vec{\nabla}_k$, with $\tilde{\omega}_k$ the angular frequency operator $\tilde{\omega}_k = -i c \vec{\nabla}_k$ where $\vec{\nabla}_k$ is merely denoted to act upon the mode k .

Also, $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ satisfies a Schrödinger-like equation for the vector potential

$$i \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \tilde{\alpha}_{0k} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (45)$$

with $\tilde{\alpha}_{0k} = \xi \tilde{\omega}_k = -i \xi c \vec{\nabla}_k$

The last two symmetrical equations can be coupled together leading to the photon *vector potential – energy* equation, a unique quantum equation expressing both the first (energy) and second (vector potential) quantization of the electromagnetic field [25,40,46]

$$i \left(\frac{\xi}{\hbar} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\tilde{\alpha}_{0k}}{\tilde{H}_k} \right) \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (46)$$

The quantization constants ξ and $\hbar$ characterize the quantization of the photon vector potential amplitude $\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = \xi\omega_k$ and energy $E_k(\omega_k) = \hbar\omega_k$ respectively.

A photon wave function related to the energy density of a single photon has already been established previously based also on the vector potential function [41]. Now, we will establish a photon wave function as a probability amplitude according to the quantum mechanics principles.

In quantum theory, the wave function normalization is generally carried out in such a way that the summation of the square of the wave function within a given volume expresses the localization probability in the said volume.

According to these concepts we may define now a wave function for the photon based precisely on the vector potential function $\tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ and taking into account the photon quantization volume since, the experiments have shown that a single photon is localizable only within a volume proportional to λ_k^3 .

Consequently, the photon wave function has to be normalized with respect to the photon quantization volume V_k and can be defined as following [48]

$$\tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_0 \omega_k}{\hbar} \right)^{1/2} \left[\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) \left(\hat{\varepsilon}_{k(L,R)} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} + \hat{\varepsilon}_{k(L,R)}^* e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} \right) \right] \quad (47)$$

where the photon spin is expressed through the helicity with left or right circular polarizations corresponding to spin $\pm\hbar$.

Note that since $\tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = \tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}^*(\vec{r}, t)$ it comes out that $\tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t)$ is a real non-local wave function.

The normalization prefactor has been chosen in such a way that

$$\left| \tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right|^2 = \frac{\varepsilon_0 \omega_k}{\hbar} \left[\xi^2 \omega_k^2 \left(\left| \hat{\varepsilon}_{k(L,R)} \right|^2 + \left| \hat{\varepsilon}_{k(L,R)}^* \right|^2 \right) \right] = \frac{2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^3}{\hbar} = \frac{1}{V_k} \quad (48)$$

so that

$$\int_{V_k} \left| \tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right|^2 d^3 r' = 1 \quad (49)$$

Therefore, when a photon is emitted in vacuum at an instant t_0 at the coordinate r_0 the probability to be localized at t around $r=r_0+ct$ on the propagation axis is normalized with respect to the quantization volume V_k .

Furthermore, $\tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t)$ satisfies Maxwell's propagation equation in vacuum

$$\bar{\nabla}_k^2 \tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = 0 \quad (50)$$

as well as the photon *vector potential – energy* quantum equation

$$i \left(\frac{\xi}{\hbar} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\tilde{\alpha}_{0k}}{\tilde{H}_k} \right) \tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (51)$$

Consequently, $\tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t)$ is a real wave function for the photon, involving the spin through the helicity corresponding to circular polarizations, and normalized with respect to the quantization volume V_k .

Obviously, according to (47) the photon wave function $\tilde{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t)$ is defined at an instant t at the coordinate r . However, the photon as a wave-corpuscule may only be conceived within a volume V_k around r as expressed by (49). In addition, its physical properties are obtained by integration of the wave properties over V_k according to (41) and (42). Consequently, in the case of the photon the mean values of the energy and momentum operators can only be calculated by considering the quantization volume V_k . Hence, considering the established photon wave function the mean value of the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian in a single photon state writes

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \left\langle \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \left| \tilde{H}_k \right| \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right\rangle_{V_k} \right| = \left| \left\langle \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \left| -i\hbar c \vec{\nabla}_k \right| \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right\rangle_{V_k} \right| \\
& = \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k \left| \left(e^{i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k(L,R)} + e^{-i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k(L,R)}^* \right) \left(e^{i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k(L,R)} - e^{-i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k(L,R)}^* \right) \right| \quad (52) \\
& = \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k \left| \left(e^{2i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} - e^{-2i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} \right) \right| = \left(2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 \right) \left(V_k \left| \sin 2(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta) \right| \right)
\end{aligned}$$

The function $\left| \sin 2(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta) \right|$ varies from zero to one, which physically means that when $\left| \sin 2(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta) \right| = 1$ corresponds to the total space of the quantization volume V_k so that the mean value of the Hamiltonian is Planck's single photon energy $\left\langle \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \left| \tilde{H}_k \right| \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right\rangle_{V_k} = \hbar \omega_k$.

With the same token, the momentum operator yields the single photon momentum

$$\left| \left\langle \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \left| \vec{p}_k \right| \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right\rangle_{V_k} \right| = \left| \left\langle \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \left| -i\hbar \vec{\nabla}_k \right| \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right\rangle_{V_k} \right| = \frac{\hbar \omega_k}{c} \quad (53)$$

It also straightforward to calculate the energy density for a single photon state

$$W_k = \left| \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right|^2 \left| \left\langle \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \left| \tilde{H}_k \right| \Phi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right\rangle_{V_k} \right| = \frac{\hbar \omega_k}{V_k} = 2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 \quad (54)$$

which, by considering the photon electric and magnetic fields established in (34) and (35), is precisely equal to the classical expression

$$W_k = \frac{1}{2} \left(\varepsilon_0 |\vec{\mathcal{E}}_k|^2 + \frac{1}{\mu_0} |\vec{\mathcal{B}}_k|^2 \right) = 2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 \quad (55)$$

We have thus demonstrated the perfect equivalence between the classical and quantum energy density for a single photon. Note also, that the obtained single photon energy density is proportional to the fourth power of the frequency exactly as in the case of a classical radiating dipole [19,20].

To conclude, the photon wave function $\vec{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t)$ expressed in (47) represents a probability density normalized with respect to the intrinsic photon quantization volume V_k . In addition, it satisfies Maxwell's propagation equation in vacuum, Schrödinger's equation with the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian and a Schrödinger-like equation for the vector potential amplitude.

3.5. The electromagnetic vacuum

According to (27), (34), (35) and (41), for $\omega_k = 0$ the photon vector potential, electric and magnetic fields as well as the energy vanish. A photon, as an integral physical entity, can only be conceived for a finite frequency which corresponds to the precession of the vector potential amplitude with circular polarization over a wavelength along the propagation axis. However, the zero frequency state does not correspond to an intangible empty space because in absence of precession the vector potential amplitude per frequency still subsists. In fact, the principal function $\Xi_{k(L,R)}$ of the vector potential as expressed in (32) and (33) does not cancel and writes in both classical and quantum representations

$$\vec{\Xi}_{0(L,R)} = \xi \left(\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{(L,R)} e^{i\theta} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{(L,R)}^* e^{-i\theta} \right) \quad (56)$$

$$\vec{\Xi}_{0(L,R)} = \xi \left(\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{(L,R)} a_{k(L,R)} e^{i\theta} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{(L,R)}^* a_{k(L,R)}^+ e^{-i\theta} \right) \quad (57)$$

Hence, in absence of energy, of vector potential as well as of electric and magnetic fields, the zero frequency state $\vec{\Xi}_{0(L,R)}$ represents the electromagnetic field ground state, which corresponds to the electromagnetic vacuum. Obviously, $\vec{\Xi}_{0(L,R)}$ is a real field permeating all of space ($\lambda_k \rightarrow \infty$) carrying circular polarization and having electric potential nature with positive and negative components. It is worth underlying that it has both classical and quantum representations entailing the introduction of the fundamental concept that the electromagnetic vacuum can also be defined in classical theory.

It is clear that the phase parameter θ can take any value and consequently the electromagnetic vacuum consists of all possible states $\vec{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t)$

$$\tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \left(\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k(L,R)} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \phi)} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k(L,R)}^* e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \phi)} \right) \quad (58)$$

$$\tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \left(\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k(L,R)} a_{k(R,L)} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \phi)} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k(L,R)}^* a_{k(L,R)}^+ e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \phi)} \right) \quad (59)$$

From the photon *vector potential – energy* equation we get the equation governing the vacuum states

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} = \tilde{\omega}_k \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\alpha}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \tilde{\alpha}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (60)$$

The physical meaning of equation (60) is that real photons emerge from the vacuum states under the action of the angular frequency operator $\tilde{\omega}_k = -i c \vec{\nabla}_k$.

Consequently, using the electromagnetic vacuum we can now demonstrate the calculation of the spontaneous emission probability lifting the well-known QED ambiguity related to the electron-vacuum interaction Hamiltonian.

We recall that the Hamiltonian of an atom in the presence of an electromagnetic field writes in QED formalism within the dipole approximation [1,2]

$$H_{tot} = H_{atom} + H_{EM} + H_{int} = \sum_i \hbar \omega_i |\Psi_i\rangle \langle \Psi_i| + \sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k \left(a_{k\lambda}^+ a_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) - \vec{D} \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (61)$$

where $|\Psi_i\rangle$ in H_{atom} represent the atomic quantum levels with respective energies $\hbar \omega_i$, H_{EM} is the electromagnetic field harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian including the zero-point energy $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$,

$\vec{D} = e \vec{r}$ is the dipole moment of the bound electron and $\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)$ is the radiation electric field involved in the interaction Hamiltonian H_{int} .

The electromagnetic radiation electric field $\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)$ is deduced from Heisenberg's equation of motion by the well-known expression

$$\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) = -\frac{\partial \vec{A}(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t), \sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k \left(a_{k\lambda}^+ a_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right] \quad (62)$$

As generally quoted in the literature, the spontaneous emission rate is calculated in QED *neglecting* the zero-point energy term in the electromagnetic field Hamiltonian [1,2]. Furthermore, the zero-point

energy $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ is a constant so that $\left[\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t), \sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k \right] = 0$ in the radiation electric field $\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)$ and

consequently the vacuum term has absolutely no contribution to the interaction Hamiltonian used to calculate the spontaneous emission in QED.

Surprisingly, with the aim of calculating the interaction between an electron and the quantum vacuum the electric field attributed to the vacuum is casted aside in both H_{EM} and H_{int} .

As mentioned previously, this well-known ambiguity in QED is due to the fact that the spontaneous emission is calculated based on the properties of the photon creation and annihilation operators, $a_{k\lambda}^+$ and $a_{k\lambda}$ respectively, and not by using the zero-point energy. In addition, it comes out from (62) that, since the vacuum state in QED is not described by a function of $a_{k\lambda}^+$ and $a_{k\lambda}$ operators, an electron-vacuum interaction Hamiltonian cannot be defined.

Conversely, the electromagnetic vacuum states expressed by $\tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm}(\vec{r}, t)$ in (59) do depend on the single photon creation and annihilation operators. Consequently, it is straightforward to define an interaction Hamiltonian per mode between an electron and the vacuum

$$H_{int} = \frac{\hbar e}{m_e c} \tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm} \tilde{\omega}_k = -i \hbar \frac{e}{m_e} \tilde{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}^{\pm} \vec{\nabla}_k \quad (63)$$

where m_e is the electron mass.

Applying first order time dependent perturbation theory the spontaneous emission rate can now be readily calculated with similar procedure as in QED theory [39,40].

The Lamb shift is calculated as usual using the photon creation operator while it can be readily demonstrated that any particle accelerated in the electromagnetic vacuum field experiences the Fulling-Davies-Unruh temperature [43]. Finally, based on the fact that the single photon electric field amplitude is proportional to the square of the frequency, it has been shown that the electromagnetic vacuum fluctuations reproduce a vacuum energy density comparable to the astrophysical observations [47].

Consequently, the electromagnetic vacuum complements the normal ordering Hamiltonian and confers a real physical state to the vacuum expressed in both classical and quantum theories.

Now, as discussed above and in order to get a physical description, a k -mode photon is a vacuum k -mode state $\Xi_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t)$ upon which the corresponding frequency ω_k is applied. Thus, it becomes clear that the electromagnetic vacuum is the real physical basis of the photon and of its wave function

$$\vec{\Phi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\epsilon_0 \omega_k^3}{\hbar} \right)^{1/2} \vec{\Xi}_{k(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (64)$$

When a k -mode photon with polarization λ is created in space the electromagnetic vacuum is depleted by the corresponding k -mode and λ -polarization vacuum state. We may conceive that immediately after this process the creation of a new photon at the same frequency carry an opposite polarization laying down new hints for understanding entanglement.

4. Conclusions

The vector potential quantization at a single photon level remedies the QED fundamental drawbacks. Thus, the photon vector potential amplitude operators as well as the electric and magnetic field amplitudes are defined independently on any external volume parameter. Also, the single photon electric and magnetic fields amplitudes in vacuum are directly proportional to the square of the frequency.

Regarding the principal singularity related to the zero-point energy, it can be eliminated by considering the normal ordering Hamiltonian coupled to the electromagnetic vacuum which has both classical and quantum representations. The last one is a zero-energy universal field expressed through the photon creation and annihilation operators and permits to establish an interaction Hamiltonian between the electrons and the vacuum states. This removes the ambiguity related to the zero-point energy in the interaction Hamiltonian for the vacuum effects. The concept of the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian for the electromagnetic field, resulting from the unjustified mean value of the normal and antinormal order Hamiltonians, has to be appraised.

In addition, the density of states theory ascribes an intrinsic quantization volume to single photons. The energy normalization of the a single mode plane electromagnetic wave over a period using the enhancement of the vector potential amplitude to single photon level confirms precisely the photon quantization volume issued from the density of states theory. Hence, the quantum properties of a single photon, energy and momentum, are not carried by a point but by a wave-corpuscule characterized by the quantization volume whose spatial dimensions are proportional to the cube of the wavelength. Heisenberg's uncertainty of position and momentum is due precisely to the photon intrinsic quantization volume.

Consequently, single photons are neither point particles nor harmonic oscillators. They constitute a particular case in the standard particle model.

A photon wave function is established normalized with respect to the quantization volume and satisfying Schrödinger's equation for the energy and the vector potential as well as Maxwell's propagation equation in vacuum. Furthermore, it depends directly on the electromagnetic vacuum states envisioning new hints for understanding the entangled states.

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